

Synthesis of High Nuclearity Osmium Carbonyl Clusters by Vacuum Pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$

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Manuscript received 17 September 1993

The vacuum pyrolysis of the activated triosmium cluster $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ has been investigated over a range of temperatures. A series of neutral and anionic clusters including $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$, $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{11}(\text{NCMe})]$, $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$, $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{20}(\text{NCMe})]$, $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{19}(\text{NCMe})_2]$, $[\text{Os}_5\text{H}(\text{CO})_{15}]^-$, $[\text{Os}_8(\text{CO})_{22}]^{2-}$, $[\text{Os}_9\text{H}(\text{CO})_{24}]^-$, $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$, $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$, $[\text{Os}_{17}(\text{CO})_{36}]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ have been identified. The production of the higher nuclearity clusters is favoured by higher reaction temperatures, and the optimum conditions for the production of a particular cluster are described. A possible mechanism for the buildup of the higher nuclearity clusters is discussed.

The most effective method for the synthesis of high nuclearity osmium carbonyl clusters is by pyrolysis of mononuclear or trinuclear starting materials, such as $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ and its derivatives¹. The reactions have been carried out either in the solid state under vacuum or in high boiling inert solvents, such as *n*-octane, diglyme, etc. The perceived mechanism for the formation of high nuclearity carbonyl clusters by this method is the thermolytic generation of the metal carbonyl fragments from the starting materials which combine to generate high nuclearity carbonyl clusters. Condensation processes under such conditions are rarely specific and inevitably lead to the formation of a wide range of products. However, recent work in this area shows that certain nuclearities (4, 6, 10, 20) appear to be favoured². A large number of high nuclearity carbonyl clusters of osmium have been prepared from the pyrolysis $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ and its derivatives in vacuum or in inert solvents^{1,3}. Although the mechanism of cluster buildup in these reactions is not well understood, factors such as temperature, heating time, charge ratio (starting materials to volume of pyrolysis tube used) and the initial pressure of the sealed pyrolysis tube (amount of residual air present) have been suggested as factors which influence the formation of high nuclearity carbonyl clusters⁴. For instance, in the vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$, a higher temperature and longer reaction time tends to favour the formation of larger clusters and carbido clusters. It has been shown that the formation of some high

nuclearity carbonyl clusters of osmium, such as $[\text{Os}_5\text{C}(\text{CO})_{15}]^5$ and $[\text{Os}_{11}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{27}]^{2-6}$ are sensitive to the amount of air present in the pyrolysis tube.

Addition of small amounts of coordinating molecules or their precursors, such as water, elemental sulphur or cyclic alkyl or acylphosphorus compounds in the pyrolysis results in the isolation of wide range of different nuclearity osmium carbonyl clusters containing hydrido⁷, sulphido⁸, alkyl or acylphosphine⁹ groups. Pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ derivatives, very often, shows a radical change in the products and their distribution. $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{11}\text{P}(\text{OMe})_3]$ gives a good conversion to Os_5 carbido clusters but no clusters of higher nuclearity can be isolated¹⁰. $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{11}\text{py}]$ also gives some Os_5 carbido clusters on heating but the major product of this reaction is $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-11}$.

In the search of the new synthetic routes to high nuclearity carbonyl clusters of osmium, pyrolysis of the $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ derivatives seems to be very promising. We now report the preparation of some high nuclearity osmium carbonyl clusters from the solid state vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ and a possible cluster buildup sequence. Preliminary reports on the isolation and structural characterisation of a number of these high nuclearity clusters have appeared elsewhere^{2, 12-14}.

Results and Discussion

Thermolytic treatment of a solid sample of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ under vacuum conditions (10^{-1} to 10^{-5} torr) at various temperatures (100° to 330°) for different lengths of time has been

investigated. At 100°, a green solid mixture of clusters is obtained. Separation by tlc on silica gives a range of Os₃ and Os₆ clusters, [Os₃(CO)₁₂] (7%), [Os₃(CO)₁₁(NCMe)] (22%), [Os₆(CO)₁₈] (11%), [Os₆(CO)₂₀(NCMe)] (20%), [Os₆(CO)₁₉(NCMe)₂] (12%) and some uncharacterised compounds in very low yields. It is interesting to note that the 'raft-like' Os₆ compounds are among the major products. This observation suggests that the simple coupling of two [Os₃(CO)₁₀(NCMe)₂] clusters or two other Os₃ units is an important step in the cluster buildup sequence. It has been shown that two [Os₃(CO)₁₀(NCMe)₂] couple to give [Os₆(CO)_{21-n}(NCMe)_n] (n = 1, 2) in the presence of catalytic quantities Pd²⁺ salts in CH₂Cl₂ at room temperature¹⁵.

Pyrolysis of [Os₃(CO)₁₀(NCMe)₂] at 130° gives a greenish brown solid mixture consisting of [Os₃(CO)₁₂] (11%), [Os₆(CO)₁₈] (7.5%), [Os₆(CO)₂₀(NCMe)] (15%), [Os₆(CO)₁₉(NCMe)₂] (17%), [HOs₅(CO)₁₅]⁻ (10%) and [Os₈(CO)₂₂]²⁻ (25%). It is believed that the anionic clusters [HOs₅(CO)₁₅]⁻ and [Os₈(CO)₂₂]²⁻ originate from the dihydrido clusters [H₂Os₅(CO)₁₅] and [H₂Os₈(CO)₂₂] which deprotonate to give the corresponding anions during the workup. It is worth noting that pyrolysis of [Os₃(CO)₁₀(NCMe)₂] under these conditions provides a better route to Os₅ and Os₈ carbonyl clusters, on the basis of their yields and simplicity of the workup procedures, than is obtained from the pyrolysis of [Os₃(CO)₁₂]³.

Pyrolysis of [Os₃(CO)₁₀(NCMe)₂] at 150° for 16 h gives three new compounds in low to moderate yields which are formulated as [HOs₉(CO)₂₄]⁻ (15%), [Os₁₀(CO)₂₆]²⁻ (10%) and [Os₁₀(CO)₂₇]²⁻ (>5%), on the basis of their spectroscopic data, and single crystals X-ray structure analyses in the case of [HOs₉(CO)₂₄]⁻¹³ and [Os₁₀(CO)₂₆]²⁻¹⁴. The yields of these new clusters can be improved by increasing the temperature of pyrolysis up to 200°. The optimum temperatures for the formation of [HOs₉(CO)₂₄]⁻ and [Os₁₀(CO)₂₆]²⁻ are 170 and 190° respectively. However, the yield of [Os₁₀(CO)₂₇]²⁻ does not show any significant dependence on temperature. From this work, it is clear that to a certain extent, the nuclearity of osmium carbonyl clusters increase as the temperature of pyrolysis increases. However, along with this general trend, the observations that (i) no Os₄ compounds and (ii) very little [Os₅(CO)₁₆] and [Os₇(CO)₂₁] are

produced throughout the temperature range investigated suggests some other factors, such as kinetic stability of the compounds, may be also important in the cluster buildup process.

Vacuum pyrolysis of [Os₃(CO)₁₀(NCMe)₂] in the temperature range of 200–220° gives an interesting observation. The yield of [Os₁₀(CO)₂₆]²⁻ decreases and the known carbido species [Os₁₀C(CO)₂₄]²⁻ gradually increases as the temperature is raised. In the same reaction, trace amounts of the large cluster [Os₂₀(CO)₄₀]²⁻ can also be isolated. This observation leads to the speculation that [Os₁₀(CO)₂₆]²⁻ is the common precursor for the [Os₁₀C(CO)₂₄]²⁻ and [Os₂₀(CO)₄₀]²⁻. In order to establish the relationship between these three compounds, [Os₁₀(CO)₂₆]²⁻ was isolated, as the Na⁺ salt, the Bu₄P⁺ salt or as the neutral dihydrido complex [H₂Os₁₀(CO)₂₆], and pyrolysed at different temperatures. At 230°, [Os₁₀(CO)₂₆]²⁻ converts to [Os₁₀C(CO)₂₄]²⁻ in excellent yield (>85%) and trace amounts of [Os₂₀(CO)₄₀]²⁻ are also produced. However, more appreciable amounts (~25%) of [Os₂₀(CO)₄₀]²⁻ are produced along with [Os₁₀C(CO)₂₄]²⁻ (~65%) at 300°. In this reaction, CO and CO₂ evolved have been trapped and identified by the characteristic P and R bands of the ν_{CO} absorption from ir spectroscopy (ν_{CO2}, centred at 2 352 cm⁻¹; ν_{CO}; centred at 2 143 cm⁻¹ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Vacuum pyrolysis of [Os₃(CO)₁₀(NCMe)₂] at temperatures above 220° gives essentially [Os₁₀C(CO)₂₄]²⁻, [Os₁₇(CO)₃₆]²⁻,¹² and [Os₂₀(CO)₄₀]²⁻, although trace amounts of [Os₃(CO)₁₂] and [HOs₅(CO)₁₅]⁻ are also isolated. The analysis of the yields of these important compounds at a series of temperatures in the range 220–300° at different initial pressures was carried out in order to establish the optimum condition for the preparation of these compounds, and perhaps cast some light on the conditions necessary for cluster buildup.

It has been suggested that the formation of high nuclearity clusters is strongly affected by the temperature, the initial pressure, the charge ratio and the heating time. To study the effect of the

temperature, the initial pressure of the pyrolysis tube (10^{-3} torr) and the charge ratio (starting material to the capacity of the pyrolysis tube) $1.0 \text{ g}/180 \text{ cm}^3$, $5.92 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$) were kept constant. Solid samples of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ were heated over a range of temperatures (220 , 240 , 260 , 280 and 300°) for 60 h. The yields of $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$, $[\text{Os}_{17}(\text{CO})_{36}]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ at different temperatures are presented graphically in Fig. 1. It clearly shows that the yield of $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ increases with increasing temperature at the expense of $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$. This is consistent with the fact that they are derived from the same precursor compound $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$. Also it would appear that $[\text{Os}_{17}(\text{CO})_{36}]^{2-}$ is formed in very low yield below 220° , but once it is formed, the yield is not significantly affected by increasing temperature. It would seem obvious from the plot, that to increase the yield of $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$, a higher temperature should be used. In practice it has been found that in doing so, large amounts of a black insoluble material were produced, which could not be characterised. Although, the solid state (CsI disk) ir spectrum of the black powder shows strong absorption at $2000\text{--}2100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicates the presence of carbonyl clusters.

Fig. 1. The yield of high nuclearity osmium carbonyl clusters from the vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ in the temperature range $220\text{--}300^\circ$.

To study the effect of initial pressure, pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at 280° at different pressures (10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} torr) inside the Carius tube has been carried out. However, no clear relationship between the yields of these high nuclearity clusters and the pressure has been observed. The effect of charge to volume

ratio has been studied by a parallel experiment of pyrolysing using same amount of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ (1.0 g) in two Carius tubes with different capacities (15 and 180 cm^3) at 170° for 60 h. A significant inhibiting effect on the cluster buildup is observed on using higher charge to volume ratio of starting material. The major products for the pyrolysis with lower charge to volume ratio (5.9 mmol dm^{-3}) are $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$, $[\text{HOs}_9(\text{CO})_{24}]^-$ and $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$. On the other hand, the major products are $[\text{HOs}_5(\text{CO})_{15}]^-$ and $[\text{Os}_8(\text{CO})_{22}]^{2-}$ for the one with higher charge to volume ratio (71 mmol dm^{-3}) and no clusters with higher nuclearity can be isolated.

One of the disadvantages for the preparation of high nuclearity clusters by vacuum pyrolysis is the long reaction time required. For example, it has been reported that the vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]^{16}$ takes at least 60 h to produce an equilibrium mixture of high nuclearity clusters composed of $[\text{Os}_5(\text{CO})_{16}]$, $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$, $[\text{Os}_7(\text{CO})_{21}]$, $[\text{Os}_8(\text{CO})_{23}]$, $[\text{Os}_5\text{C}(\text{CO})_{15}]$ and $[\text{Os}_8\text{C}(\text{CO})_{22}]$. The synthetic value of this reaction is greatly hampered by the long reaction time required. To study the effect of reaction time on the pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$, a solid sample at standardised conditions (10^{-3} torr, 170° and 5.7 mmol dm^{-3}) was pyrolysed for different lengths of time (12 and 72 h). There is no significant difference in the yields of products and their distribution. The same experiment was repeated at 300° and gave a similar observation. This suggests that the reaction is essentially attaining equilibrium after 12 h.

The synthesis of the high nuclearity clusters of osmium by the pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ and its derivatives in vacuo is most widely used. However, the reaction conditions employed, and the complex mixture of products obtained, make an understanding of the mechanism of cluster buildup process very difficult. However, on the basis of this work, it is possible to extract some information on the cluster growth process and propose some possible mechanisms for the formation of high nuclearity osmium carbonyl clusters. The formation of $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{21-n}(\text{NCMe})_n]$ ($n = 1, 2$) over the temperature range $100\text{--}130^\circ$ from solid $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ suggests that the coupling of two Os_3 units is a key step for the cluster buildup. Since the relative orientation of molecules is a key

factor in a solid state reaction, knowing the packing of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ in the solid state will aid to our understanding of the reaction mechanism. Stereoview of packing diagrams of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ ¹⁷ projected down three different unit cell axes are shown in Fig. 2. Molecules of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ pack in three-dimensions in such a way that two Os_3 triangular units are parallel and the Os–Os edge with the substituted acetonitrile ligands face each other. It is likely that this favourable relative orientation of molecules is related to the facile formation of the Os_6 'raft-like' molecules, because heating of an

octane solution of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at 100–130° for 5 h produces only minute quantity of $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{21-n}(\text{NCMe})_n]$ ($n = 1, 2$).

At 150°, all the 'raft-like' Os_6 clusters produced are converted to $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$. This conversion has been demonstrated by heating some preformed $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{21-n}(\text{NCMe})_n]$ ($n = 1, 2$) in vacuo. It is believed that the successive capping of mononuclear $\text{Os}(\text{CO})_n$ fragments on $\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}$ produces Os_7 , Os_8 , Os_9 and Os_{10} clusters. Products and their distribution are determined by the temperature of pyrolysis. A trace amount of liquid, which is thought to be mononuclear osmium compounds can be seen when the pyrolysis tube is cooled down. Unfortunately, attempts to trap and characterise these unknown materials have been met with little success so far.

Vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$ at a temperature of 210° gives essentially $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ and a trace of $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$. We believe that $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ is produced via a disproportionation reaction of CO to give carbido clusters and CO_2 , and $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ probably forms either by a coupling of two $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$ molecules and follows by substantial metal core re-arrangement or via a rearrangement of the $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$ metal core first, to give some geometrically favourable fragments of $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$, the couples together to give the observed structure of $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$. A schematic drawing of the proposed mechanism for the cluster buildup by vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ is shown in Fig. 3. Those compounds with known structures are illustrated with drawings of their metal cores.

Experimental

The solvents were distilled prior to use under nitrogen atmosphere, over the appropriate drying agent. Routine separation of products was performed by thin layer chromatography using laboratory prepared glass plates coated to 1 mm thickness with Merck-Kieselgel 60F₂₅₄ silica gel. Infrared spectra were recorded as solution except the trapping of gaseous product experiments, in 0.5 mm CaF_2 cells on a Perkin-Elmer PE 983 or a PE 1710 Fourier-transform spectrometers. Mass spectra were recorded using a Kratos-F.A.B.-MS50 or a Kratos-F.A.B.-MS902 mass spectrometers.

Fig. 2 Stereoview of packing diagrams of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$: (a) projection down a axis, (b) projection down b axis and (c) projection down c axis

The brown black microcrystalline solid was extracted from the tube using acetone until the tube was empty. The resulting suspension was made up to 200 cm³ in volume using acetone, and excess $[(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{N}]^+\text{Cl}^-$ (1.0 g, 1.75 mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 24 h to give a dark red-brown solution. The solution was reduced in volume and the black insoluble material was filtered. The brown-red solution was separated by tlc (thick plate) using acetone-hexane (50 : 50) as eluent. The high nuclearity carbonyl cluster products found on the plates were $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$, seen as a thick red-brown band ($R_f \sim 0.55$); $[\text{Os}_{17}(\text{CO})_{36}]^{2-}$, seen as a thin dark brown band on top of $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ ($R_f \sim 0.60$); $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$, seen as a thick green brown band ($R_f \sim 0.40$).

The respective products were scraped off from the plates and extracted using acetone. The solutions were filtered through celite to remove the very fine silica and evaporated off in vacuo to give microcrystalline products in varying yields depending on the temperature of pyrolysis. Apart from the high nuclearity carbonyl cluster products isolated, a thin yellow band of low nuclearity clusters (major component $[\text{HOs}_5(\text{CO})_{15}]^-$ ($R_f \sim 0.9$) and a thin dark brown band below $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ ($R_f \sim 0.1$), which has not yet been characterised, were obtained.

Vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at medium temperatures (150–210°): To a flame-dried Carius tube (180 cm³ capacity), solid $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ (1.0 g, 1.07 mmol) was introduced as a slurry suspension in small amount of n-hexane (5 cm³). The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give a thin layer of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ deposit on the inner wall of the pyrolysis tube. The Carius tube was evacuated to 10⁻³ torr for 2 h and sealed at this pressure. The Carius inserted into a steel liner and placed into an oven and heated at the required temperature (150–210°) for 16–28 h.

A dark brown powder and a yellow crystalline solid $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ were obtained. The resulting solid mixture was first extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (50 cm³) to give a brown CH_2Cl_2 insoluble powder which was extracted in acetone (10 cm³) to give a dark brown solution and a yellow powder of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$. The CH_2Cl_2 extract was reduced in volume and separated by tlc (thick plate) using CH_2Cl_2 -hexane (15 : 85) as eluent. An array of products were

obtained in decreasing R_f values as follows : $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ ($R_f \sim 0.80$), $[\text{Os}_5(\text{CO})_{16}]$ ($R_f \sim 0.65$), $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$ ($R_f \sim 0.60$), $[\text{Os}_7(\text{CO})_{21}]$ ($R_f \sim 0.50$) and $[\text{Os}_8(\text{CO})_{23}]$ ($R_f \sim 0.45$) in varying yields depending on the temperature of pyrolysis.

The acetone extract was separated by tlc (thick plate) using acetone-hexane (50 : 50) as eluent. An orange-brown band of $[\text{HOs}_9(\text{CO})_{24}]^-$ ($R_f \sim 0.6$), a brown band of $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{27}]^{2-}$ ($R_f \sim 0.5$) and a dark brown band consisting of basically $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$ and trace amount of $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Os}_{17}(\text{CO})_{36}]^{2-}$ ($R_f \sim 0.2$), which increase as temperature of pyrolysis increase were obtained. Further separation of this dark brown band was achieved by tlc (thin plate) using acetone-hexane (60 : 40) as eluent. The dark brown $[\text{Os}_{17}(\text{CO})_{36}]^{2-}$ ($R_f \sim 0.50$) and red $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ ($R_f \sim 0.45$) were marginally separated from the dark brown $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$ ($R_f \sim 0.40$).

Vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at 130°: A similar procedure to that in vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at medium temperatures was adopted. In a typical experiment $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ (1.0 g, 1.07 mmol) heated at 130° for 16 h gave $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ (110 mg, 11%), $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{11}(\text{NCMe})]$ (42 mg, 4.3%), $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$ (65 mg, 7.5%), $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{20}(\text{NCMe})]$ (137 mg, 15%), $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{19}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ (162 mg, 17%), $[\text{HOs}_5(\text{CO})_{15}]^-$ (128 mg, 10% as $[(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{N}]^+$ salt) and $[\text{Os}_8(\text{CO})_{22}]^{2-}$ (322 mg, 25% as $[(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{N}]^+$ salt) after separation on tlc (thin plate) eluting with CH_2Cl_2 -hexane (40 : 60).

Vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at 100°: A similar procedure to that in vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at medium temperatures was adopted. In a typical experiment $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ (1.0 g, 1.07 mmol) heated at 100° for 14 h gave a green-blue residue which was dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (25 cm³). Separation by tlc (thin plate) using CH_2Cl_2 -hexane (60 : 40) as eluent gave $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ (65 mg, 7%), $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{11}(\text{NCMe})]$ (206 mg, 22%), $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$ (87 mg, 11%), $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{20}(\text{NCMe})]$ (110 mg, 12%), $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{19}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ (184 mg, 20%), a blue and a yellow uncharacterised products in minute quantity.

Vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$ anion: An acetone solution of $[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]^{2-}$ prepared from the vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2]$ at 170° was introduced in a dried Carius tube (60 cm³ capacity) and the solvent was removed and the tube

was evacuated at 10^{-3} torr for 1 h. It was then sealed and heated in an oven at 230° for 12 h. The tube was opened and the dark brown solid was dissolved in acetone. Separation by tlc (thin plate) eluted with acetone-hexane (55 : 45) gave a major red band of $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ and a very thin green band of $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ as evidenced from ir spectroscopy and mass spectrometry.

The experiment was repeated at 300° with identical workup procedures. The amount of $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ was substantially increased compared with previous experiment at 230° . The ratio of $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Os}_{20}(\text{CO})_{40}]^{2-}$ was approximated 3 : 1. A trace amount of uncharacterised black material was also obtained.

Vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{21-n}(\text{NCMe})_n]$, $n = 1, 2$: A mixture of solid $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{21-n}(\text{NCMe})_n]$, $n = 1, 2$ (300 mg, 0.17 mmol) was placed in a dried Carius tube (60 cm³ capacity) and evacuated at 10^{-3} torr for 1 h. It was then sealed and heated in an oven at 130° for 12 h. The tube was opened and the brown solid that extracted in CH_2Cl_2 was found to be pure $[\text{Os}_6(\text{CO})_{18}]$ (225 mg, 0.14 mmol) in 80% yield. A trace amount of black material, proved insoluble in most common organic solvents, remained uncharacterised.

Vacuum pyrolysis of $[\text{Bu}_4\text{P}]_2[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]$ -Trapping of gaseous products : Finely powdered $[\text{Bu}_4\text{P}]_2[\text{Os}_{10}(\text{CO})_{26}]$ (20 mg, 0.006 mmol) was placed in the bulb in the floor of an infrared gas cell with CsI windows and path-length 10 cm. The cell was then evacuated and placed in the FT infrared spectrometer and the background spectrum was recorded. The bulb of the cell containing the reactants was then heated to ca. 170° for 5 min. The spectrum of the gaseous products was recorded. The characteristic P and R bands of the ν_{CO} mode of gaseous CO_2 could be seen centred at 2352 cm^{-1} and also the characteristic P and R bands of the ν_{CO} mode of gaseous CO of low intensity compared to those of CO_2 were present at 2143 cm^{-1} . Dissolution of the solid residues in acetone followed by tlc showed that the product of pyrolysis was $[\text{Os}_{10}\text{C}(\text{CO})_{24}]^{2-}$ and a small amount of unreacted starting material was recovered.

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